

THE ROLE OF SELF-ASSESSMENT IN DEVELOPING COMPENSATORY COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

Isroilov Sabirillo Inoxmjjon o'g'li

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Faculty of Philology

***Annotation.** Education should embrace each student's self-perception while promoting the cognitive and emotional growth of pupils with specific educational needs. Therefore, mindfulness is a learning experience that offers participants substantial advantages in terms of learning, emotional well-being, and physical and mental health. The "Multidimensional Self-Concept scale" was used in this descriptive-correlational study to examine how 26 primary school kids with compensatory education requirements perceived themselves. Positive levels of academic self-concept in mathematics, physical appearance and ability, and peer relationships were stated by the respondents.*

***Key words.** self-concept, inclusion, mindfulness, compensatory education, students*

The educational model put out by the current system emphasizes the development of students' emotional as well as cognitive capacities. Nevertheless, as education aims to provide students with the abilities, information, and attitudes necessary to support their independence and integration in social and academic contexts, it should also support the development of their personalities. Accordingly, education should respect and value students' sentiments, emotions, and self-worth; expand their options; and recognize their individuality, cultural specificities, collective identity, and uniqueness (Fernández & Terrén, 2008).

The importance of self-concept lies in the significant role it plays in character formation. According to Musitu, García, and Gutiérrez (1994), self-concept is understood as the notion an individual has of himself or herself, based on experiences with others and on how they evaluate their own behavior; this encompasses emotional, social, physical, family, and academic aspects. The

characteristics associated with self-concept based on Shavelson, Hubner, and Stanton's (1976) model are as follows:

People categorize the large quantity of knowledge they possess about themselves and build relationships with others, making it a complex process. Perceptions of self in several subareas (intellectual self-concept in language, mathematics, etc.) are arranged. A person's general self-concept is stable, but as they move down the ladder, their self-concept becomes less stable and more situation-specific. A person's self-concept becomes increasingly intricate and multidimensional as they mature.

Promote equal opportunities in education, with preference given to underprivileged sectors, based on establishing measures that effectively redress baseline inequalities; Facilitate the social and educational inclusion and integration of all students by eliminating processes of social and cultural exclusion and by developing communicative attitudes and mutual respect among all, irrespective of their cultural, linguistic, and ethnic background.

Promote the enrichment afforded by different cultures and encourage the retention and dissemination of a minority group's own language and culture; Support the active participation of social agents and the education community to ensure equal opportunities, access to education, and the inclusion of immigrant families or those finding it difficult to integrate; Drive forward coordination and collaboration efforts with different nonprofit organizations, administrative bodies, and institutions to develop compensatory education measures intended for groups who find themselves in culturally disadvantaged situations.

The aim of this study was to analyze the level of self-concept in primary school students with compensatory education needs; that is, students who find themselves in disadvantaged personal, social, economic, and cultural situations. To this end, a descriptive–correlational methodology was used, conducting data collection by way of a questionnaire. Both the aim of the study and the characteristics of the

sample group were taken into account to adapt the research process to the circumstances.

This study has focused on the analysis of perceived self-concept in primary school students with compensatory education needs. It has enabled us to define the self-concept dimensions through which the participating pupils reveal a negative image of themselves as well as others associated with the students' positive self-perceptions. From this perspective, it is possible to design a mindfulness program based on the needs and interests of the target group and which is capable of contributing toward improving the educational process, facilitating the inclusion and full autonomy of students in the school and social environment. Generally speaking, positive outcomes have been observed in students' perceptions of peer relations, physical appearance and physical ability, and academic self-concept in mathematics.

REFERENCES

1. Arguís, R. (2014). Mindfulness y Educación [Mindfulness and Education]. In A. Cebolla, J. García-Campayo, & M. Demarzo (Eds.), *Mindfulness y Ciencia. De la tradición a la modernidad* [Mindfulness and science. From tradition to modernity] (pp. 129-149).
2. Beauchemin, J., Hutchins, T., & Patterson, F. (2008). Mindfulness meditation may lessen anxiety, promote social skills, and improve academic performance among adolescents with learning disabilities. *Complementary Health Practice Review*, 131, 34-35.
3. Correlates of participation in physical activity for adolescent girls: A systematic review of recent literature. *Journal of Physical Activity & Health*, 2, 423-434.
4. Bolat, N., Doğangun, B., Yavuz, M., Demir, T., & Kayaalp, L. (2011). Depression and anxiety levels and self-concept characteristics of adolescents with congenital complete visual impairment. *Turkish Journal of Psychiatry*, 22, 77-82.